

Navigating the Tangled Web of Security Interests in Cameroon's Public Procurement Contracts: An OHADA-Centric Analysis

Agnes Ngwene-Aneweh Mbah-Fongkimeh, PhD.
*Senior Lecturer, Department of English Law, Faculty of Law and
Political Science, University of Dschang, Cameroon.*
Email: mbahagi@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Public procurement plays a vital role in economic development, serving as both a strategic tool for state function and a revenue source for private enterprises. Although procurement contracts offer financial leverage for contractors; their unique legal nature raises concerns regarding creditor security, enforcement mechanisms, and administrative prerogatives. Securitization of interests in public procurement contracts represent a double-edged sword. On the one hand, they provide a crucial financing mechanism for contractors, enabling them to fulfil large-scale public projects that drive economic growth. On the other hand, the unique nature of public contracts—characterized by administrative prerogatives, unilateral contract modifications, and the complexities of debt recovery—creates substantial risks for secured creditors. By dissecting the intersection between public contracts and security interests, this paper highlights the legal and practical challenges faced by creditors, the limitations imposed by administrative powers, and the risks associated with debt recovery within the OHADA legal framework. Ultimately, it calls for legal reforms that safeguard creditor interests while maintaining procurement efficiency, ensuring a more stable and predictable investment environment.

Keywords: Security interests, public contracts, debt recovery, risks, OHADA, Cameroon.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Public procurement serves as a cornerstone of economic activity in every state, positioning governments not only as regulators and policy-makers but also as dominant market participants. Beyond setting taxes and creating employment, governments play a pivotal role in driving the economy through the purchase of goods and services from the private sector, through the award of public procurement contracts.¹ Until recently,² public procurement did not attract more than a cursory glance in development circles.

Many developing countries today, channel significant proportions of their budgets through the procurement system³ affirming to the fact that procurement is probably one of the most indispensable elements of a thriving state. Because of its large size, African states have since been awakened to the potential of public procurement and the importance it wedges on the socio-economic welfare of any state,⁴ as well as its potential influence on other issues such as governance and development.⁵ Recognizing its strategic function, governments have increasingly prioritized procurement systems as essential mechanisms for promoting economic growth, strengthening institutional frameworks, and driving equitable development.

Public procurement stands as a cornerstone of state functionality, serving as the conduit through which governments engage with private entities for the delivery of goods, works, and services essential to sustaining public administration and providing services to citizens. At its core, a public procurement contract formalizes this partnership — a binding legal agreement whereby a contractor, supplier or service provider enters into an agreement with the state, a regional or local authority or a public establishment to carry out work or to supply goods or services against payment.⁶ Because of the sheer value of procurement contracts and high level of discretion, governments wield procurement systems not merely as operational tools, but as strategic levers for resource allocation across economic sectors. Beyond meeting public needs, procurement systems offer a

¹ Giovanni, D. *et al.*, (2022), “Government procurement and access to credit: firm dynamics and aggregate implications”, Staff Report, No. 1006, Federal Reserve Bank of New York, New York, NY. Available at <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/262056>. (Accessed October 2025).

² According to Arrowsmith, S. *et al.*, (2000), *Regulating public procurement: National and International perspectives*. The Hague Kluwer Law International, P.3, the sudden growth of interest in public procurement has been triggered by the upsurge in international efforts to create free trade amongst states. Worldwide, this growth has become a very important socio-economic factor and is described as a “procurement revolution”, marked by the negotiation of numerous regional and international agreements designed to eliminate discrimination against foreign products and suppliers in public procurement.

³ Procurement consistently represents 12.8% of the GDP in OECD countries. For details see https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/public-procurement_en. (Accessed January 2025).

⁴ Basheka, B., (2008), “Procurement planning and local governance in Uganda: A factor analysis approach”, *International Journal of Procurement*, Vol. 8, Issue 3. P.1.

⁵ McCrudden, C., (2007), *Buying social justice, Equality, government procurement and legal change*, New York, Oxford University Press. Pp. 1-30.

⁶ Law No. 2018/366 of 20 June 2018, to institute the Public Contracts Code, Article 5 (aa).

powerful mechanism to stimulate targeted sectors of the economy, empower specific firms, and ultimately drive inclusive economic growth.

As an important source of revenue for the private sector and a crucial fiscal policy tool for governments, procurement is a myriad of possibilities to the service provider and to firm growth. It has been shown that granting procurement contracts to small firms, either by directly targeting smaller firms or by slicing larger contracts into smaller ones, help these firms grow and overcome financial constraints.⁷ Besides the secure streams of cash flow, procurement can also be used as collateral to increase firms' access to credit, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) which are considered to play an indispensable role in sustainable public procurement.⁸

The question may be asked whether the necessity of securitizing interests in public procurement contracts can be avoided if the administration offers mobilization advance to contractors. The law provides that the contractor, upon a simple request addressed to the contracting authority, that is the government, may obtain a start-off advance. However, the advance usually does not exceed 20% of the initial price of the contract and must be guaranteed at 100% by a banking establishment. Also, the contracting authority makes periodic payments according to the terms of the special administrative clauses. Despite the foregoing, the contractor is in need of liquidity to complete the project and neither the start-off advance nor the periodic payments will suffice. Moreover, administrative delays and even financial constraints of the state could hinder the prompt provision of advances. Therefore, in order to execute the contract, contractors resort to the use of public procurement contracts as security for loans.

Therefore, in a bid to ensure the obtention of financing especially by thinly capitalized contractors, the public contracts code allows the government contractor to use the procurement contract as a security, subject to any form of transfer of a claim.⁹ But before that, a contractor is expected to provide a security as guarantee to the state, for proper and complete execution of the procurement contract.¹⁰ Thus the word security in the Public Contracts Code operates on two key fronts: firstly, as performance guarantees to ensure contractors fulfil their obligations and secondly, as collateral instruments enabling contractors to access financing. In the first scenario a 3rd party-surety guarantees

⁷ Giovanni, D. *et al*, (2022), *Op. Cit.*

⁸ Silva, M. & Scott, G., (2014), "Empowering small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by leveraging public procurement: Eight big ideas from Mexico", International Institute for sustainable Development. According to these authors, sustainable public procurement aims at ensuring that government spending benefits a country both environmentally and socially. By ensuring the inclusion of SMEs in the government supply chain, public procurement has the potential to achieve outstanding economic and social benefits-including the creation of skilled jobs, increased domestic tax revenue and more robust domestic economic growth.

⁹ Public Contracts Code, Article 150.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, Article 137-142.

the proper and complete execution of the procurement contract, and agrees to assume liability if the contractor defaults.¹¹

In this light, the state makes use of security interests such as guarantees, not only to mitigate potential losses, but also to compel compliance and quality delivery. On the other hand, public procurement contracts themselves can be leveraged as security interests by contractors seeking external financing. By assigning their payment claims as collateral, contractors—particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)—can unlock much-needed credit to finance their contractual obligations. This form of security protects the creditors against the contractor's bankruptcy or where the contractor is a body corporate, in the event of its liquidation.¹² Creditors are provided with the right to realize the assigned claims if the contractor defaults, effectively protecting lenders from losses arising from contractor insolvency.

This dual function of security interests underscores their vital role in stimulating private sector participation in public procurement markets. Whatever its form, a security interest is defined as the pledge, for the benefit of a creditor of an asset, a set of properties or assets to secure performance of an obligation or a set of obligations, irrespective of their legal nature whether existing or future, determined or determinable, conditional or unconditional, and whether their amount is fixed or fluctuating.¹³

Procurement Investment is a driver of development and even though investors are generally motivated by the desire to make profits from their investments, there is a much more compelling desire- the need to protect their investment against any form of loss. The inherent risks associated with these large-scale contracts demand robust mechanisms to safeguard public funds and ensure project success. Just like private firms, the state needs some kind of assurance that the infrastructure and the goods and services that are the object of multiple procurement contracts shall be delivered in good time and quality. Thus, the best form of protection of State funds and those of private investors seem to be through the use of security interests in public procurement.

The OHADA law is the main legal instrument regulating securities in all its member states.¹⁴ The Uniform Act on securities proposes a plethora of security interests that could be used by investors-the state or private firms, to protect their investment.¹⁵

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² *Ibid.*, Article 150.

¹³ OHADA Uniform Act on Security Interests, Article 1. The original Uniform Act on Securities was adopted on April 17, 1997. The applicable Uniform Act on Securities was revised and adopted in 2010. It came into force in 2011 and has remained the primary legislation governing security interests in all member states.

¹⁴ Article 10 of the OHADA Treaty 1993 provides that the Uniform Acts are directly applicable and overriding in the contracting states notwithstanding any conflict they may give rise to in respect of previous or subsequent enactment of municipal laws.

¹⁵ The uniform Act on securities, classifies securities under three broad heads. Firstly, collateral securities: these are securities provided either by individuals or by corporate bodies. There are basically two forms of collateral securities, we have the surety-bond (article 13) and the autonomous guarantees and counter guarantees (article 39). Secondly, there is the transferable guarantees. In accordance with Article 50,

Looking at the category of transferable securities, pledge over intangible assets¹⁶ seems to closely describe the notion of public contracts as security as provided by the public contracts code. However, it is worth mentioning that, the Uniform act enumerates an exhaustive list of intangible assets that can be pledged as security omitting specifically the mention of a public contract. Thus, a public contract as security stands at a legal crossroads navigating between the provisions of the OHADA Uniform Acts and the Public Contracts Code.

While the notion of pledging intangible assets such as receivables is well-entrenched in the OHADA legal framework, the conspicuous omission of public contracts as transferable securities raises fundamental questions about the intent of the legislators. Was this exclusion a deliberate attempt not to meddle in the sovereign nature of public procurement contracts, or merely an unintended gap in the harmonized legal framework? These and many more are some of the issues that have intrigued and spurred this research.

Our findings have revealed that the presence of security interests in public procurement is a dicey issue. This research posits that the use of public procurement contracts as security presents a hybrid legal construct that transcends the classic definition of security interests under the OHADA Uniform Act on Securities. Unlike conventional security interests, where the object of the pledge is a purely commercial asset, public procurement contracts involve a tripartite relationship between the state, the contractor, and the creditor — with the added layer of public interest considerations. Moreover, when it comes to ranking of securities and distribution of proceeds after a collective proceeding, recourse is made to the OHADA laws notably the Uniform Act on securities and the Uniform Act on Collective Proceedings for Clearing of Debts.¹⁷ This complex dynamic necessitates a nuanced legal framework that balances the state's sovereign prerogatives with the creditor's right to repayment and the contractor's need for financing.

The OHADA laws relevant to this study provide a comprehensive framework for creating, perfecting and realizing security interests generally. However, the application of these provisions to the unique context of public procurement contracts, presents a multifaceted challenge. An in-depth analysis of this specific kind of security will inform

transferable guarantees shall include: possessory lien, property retained or ceded as guarantee, pledge over tangible moveable assets, pledge over intangible assets and preferential rights. Finally, we have mortgages as the third category of securities- this will involve security over real estate for example over land and buildings. Mortgages can either be contractual or forcibly created either by law or by court decision.

¹⁶ Article 125 Uniform Act on securities provides for the assignment of intangible assets as security. Article 126 further provides a list of the kinds of intangible assets that can be pledged as security: receivables; bank account; rights of partners, securities and financial instruments accounts; business/goodwill and intellectual property rights.

¹⁷ The older version of the Uniform Act on Collective proceedings was adopted on April 10 1998, it entered into force on January 1, 1999. The relevant and currently applicable Uniform Act on Collective Proceedings came into force on December 24, 2015.

the stakeholders of its peculiarities, effectiveness or otherwise. Given the inextricable link between public procurement and economic development, the practice of leveraging public contracts as collateral will continue to gain prominence. However, the lack of explicit legal recognition of public contracts as security within the OHADA framework poses significant legal uncertainties for creditors, contractors, and regulators alike. This research will analyze relevant provisions of the OHADA Uniform Acts in the context of securities interests. While hoping to shed more light on the legal peculiarities, practical challenges, and potential reforms necessary to enhance the effectiveness of public procurement contracts as security interests. It is hoped that this work will contribute to the broader discourse on security interests in commercial transactions by proffering a deeper understanding of this crucial aspect of business law.

2. THE SPECIFICITIES AND FORMS OF SECURITY INTERESTS IN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT CONTRACTS

As mentioned earlier, the Uniform Act on Securities is completely silent on the issue of public contracts as a form of security. Consequently, a better understanding of this aspect of security interest, necessitates a reading of the public contracts code coupled with relevant notions of administrative law. Security interests in public procurement present some special features distinct from the classic notion of securities. These peculiarities appear not only in the form of claims that could result from a procurement contract but also from the uniqueness inherent in the security itself.

2.1 Mandatory Guarantees Required in Public Procurement Contracts

The execution of public procurement contracts generally entails the mobilization of enormous financial resources which most often than not, exceeds the financial capacity of the contracting firms. The possibility of using public procurement contracts as security for loans is to facilitate the execution of such contracts by the contracting firms. Public procurement regulations universally mandate that every contract holder must furnish guarantees. This requirement aligns with the broader principle of financial prudence in public expenditure while reinforcing the contractor's obligation to complete the project under the agreed terms.

Every public contract holder must provide guarantees from duly approved and recognized financial institutions or by a personal joint and several guarantee,¹⁸ whereby they undertake to pay, sums for which the administration's contracting partner may be liable under the contract.¹⁹ The guarantee referred to here is an agreement between the contractor and the financial institution or individual, whereby the latter undertakes to perform an existing or future obligation contracted by the bidder or contractor in the

¹⁸ Public Contracts Code, Article 140.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, Article 140(4).

event where he defaults²⁰ or the guarantor enters an agreement with the contractor also known as the principal, where he undertakes to pay a fixed amount to the project owner upon the latter's first call.²¹ Therefore, our position on the Uniform Act on Securities is that the guarantees required in procurement can either be a surety-bond or an autonomous guarantee depending on the particular circumstance.

2.1.1 The Bid Bond

The very first guarantee in the procurement process, required of all bidders is a 'bid bond'. A bid bond is a guarantee that a service provider will enter into a contract with the administration if they are the successful bidder. This is a security that has multiple functions: it protects the project owner from financial loss if the contractor backs out of the deal; it ensures that contractors are serious about their bids and will not submit frivolous bids and it pre-qualifies contractors since only financially stable contractors will be able to obtain a bond.²² The Public Contracts Code provides that each bidder must include a bid bond, where required in his bid.²³ If the winning contractor signs the contract, the bid bond is no longer needed, if he however refuses to sign the contract, the project owner can make a claim against the bid bond to cover the costs of finding another contractor. The bid bond requirements vary depending on the volume of the contract. The specific tender documents for each public contract will provide the definitive and mandatory amount for the bid bond in compliance with legal provisions.²⁴ While the Public Contracts Code, is the overarching law, the specific detail regarding 2% maximum for bid bond is found in related decrees²⁵ but is generally applied as a reference for bid bonds in broader public procurement in Cameroon.

2.1.2 The Final Bond

After the bidding process, is the contract evaluation and award phase. The successful bidder who becomes the contractor or the contract holder, is bound to provide a security as guarantee for the complete execution of the contract known as the 'final bond'.²⁶ This is also known as a completion bond and guarantees that the project will be completed on

²⁰ Uniform Act on Securities, Article 13.

²¹ *Ibid.*, Article 39.

²² We hold the view that a bid bond is an autonomous guarantee as provided by the Uniform Act on Securities mentioned above. This is because, the guarantor simply undertakes to pay a fixed amount to the beneficiary upon the latter's first call.

²³ Public Contracts Code, Article 90(1). Instead of bid bonds, small and medium sized enterprises owned and managed by nationals, as well as civil society organizations may produce either a certified cheque, a bank cheque, a legal mortgage or a guarantee by a bank or a financial establishment duly approved in accordance with the instruments in force-Article 90(7) For services under jobbing orders, certified cheques and bank cheques shall be accepted in lieu of the bid bond- Article 90(9).

²⁴ Article 39 (1) of Decree No. 2018/355 of June 12, 2018, fixing the common rules applicable to contracts of public enterprises, provides that the bid bond, the amount of which is a lump sum, shall not exceed 2% of the provisional estimated cost of the project.

²⁵ Decree No. 2018/355 of June 12, 2018, fixing the common rules applicable to contracts of public enterprises, *Op. Cit.*

²⁶ *Ibid.*, Article 137 (a).

time and according to contract specifications. The final bond is constituted within 20 calendar days following the notification of the contract and may not be less than 2% or more than 5% of the value of the contract. This bond must cover the period for the delivery of services up to their provisional acceptance.²⁷

2.1.3 The Performance Bond

Besides the final bond, each contract holder must provide another security where applicable, known as the 'performance bond'.²⁸ This bond serves two principal purposes: for one, it serves as guarantee for the proper execution of the contract, covering the guarantee or maintenance period up to final acceptance. The project owner through a performance bond is protected against defects and secondly, the performance bond serves as a replacement of a retention bond which is normally a percentage held back or deducted from the payments due the contractor until the project is completed and a certain period known as defects liability period²⁹ has passed. With the performance bond issued by a surety company, the administration will no longer retain a percentage, usually 10% of the contract amount. The performance bond is beneficial to the contractor who receives full payment of the project upon completion, without having to chase the release of the retention bond. This improves their cash flow and equally permits them invest in order ventures.

The use of guarantees in public procurement is a mandatory safeguard put in place to ensure that contract holders provide the administration with appropriate security to ensure the proper, complete and timely execution of procurement contracts. There also exists other security interests that could be attached to a public procurement contract to enable contractors obtain commercial loans.

3. THE USE OF PUBLIC CONTRACTS AS SECURITY FOR COMMERCIAL LOANS

The Public Contracts Code provides unequivocally that any procurement contract concluded in accordance with the code, may be used as security and subject to any form of transfer of claim.³⁰ This position affirms the fact that, public contracts, while primarily aimed at fulfilling public needs, can also serve as valuable security for raising funds. This practice allows contractors whether they be the main contractors, or sub-contractors to leverage their existing or future revenue streams from government projects to secure commercial loans used for the financing of the contract itself or other credit schemes. The

²⁷ Public Contracts Code, Articles 138-139.

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ Where a public contract has a guarantee period or maintenance period, the contractor is liable to rectify any defects within this period. The retention money or performance bond can be used to cover the costs of repairs if the contractor fails to do so.

³⁰ Public Contracts Code, Article 150.

code further provides that a public contract can be subject to any form of transfer of claim. This simply means that contractors can attach any kind of claim to the public contract, subject to its conformity with existing legislations, in exchange for a loan. A perusal of the Uniform Act on Securities highlights the fact that, based on its nature, a public contract can be used to create two types of security interests: contractors can either assign their receivables or they can create a pledge with the contract which is an intangible asset.

3.1 Assignment Of Receivables from Public Contracts as Security

An assignment of receivables is a lending agreement where a debt owed to a third party may be assigned as security for any credit granted by a national or a foreign legal entity conducting banking or credit operations in the regular course of business for its own account.³¹ The above definition proffered by the Uniform Act on Securities, lacks some clarity. In simple terms, an assignment of receivables as security in procurement, is a lending agreement where a business, in this case a contract holder, transfers its accounts receivables or money he hopes to receive for the execution of the contract, to a lender as collateral for a loan. The lender can collect the accounts receivables if the business does not repay the loan. As an intangible asset, the contract itself does not require physical possession or transfer, but its value is derived from the future payments that are expected under the contract.

This is a form of chose in action³² assignment, dealing with intangible personal property rights. It is distinct from a simple debt assignment where ownership of the debt is fully transferred. In the case of assignment of debts or receivables as security, the assignor retains an 'equity of redemption', because this arrangement is not an outright sale of the debt. The assignor retains an interest, and the transfer is conditional, typically reverting to the assignor upon fulfilment of the secured obligation. The Uniform Act on Securities does not list out the types of debts that can be assigned. However, chose in action or such debts include: account receivables or money owed for goods and services; ordinary contract debts; negotiable instruments; investment securities; insurance policies; intellectual property rights and even rights to damages founded on tort actions.³³

The assignment of a debt or receivables resulting from a procurement contract, involves three parties: the debtor who is the administration; the assignor who is the contract holder; and the assignee who is the creditor or credit institution. The object of the assignment is the debt or receivables owed to the contract holder by the

³¹ Uniform Act on Securities, Article 80.

³² Holdsworth, W. S. (1920), "The History of the Treatment of "Choses" in Action by the Common Law", *Harvard Law Review*, Vol. 33. P. 997. A definition of a 'chose in action', which is generally accepted as correct, was given by Channel J in *Torkington v Magee*: a chose in action is 'a known legal expression used to describe all personal rights of property which can only be claimed or enforced by action, and not by taking physical possession.

³³ Wood, P. R. (1995), *Comparative law of security and guarantees*, London, Sweet & Maxwell. P. 33.

administration for the execution of the procurement contract. The debt in question must be clearly defined and the assignee is thus a secured creditor,³⁴ and his security interests generally takes priority over later claims to the same debt provided the assignment is perfected by notice to the project owner³⁵ or registration in the register of commerce and security.³⁶

The legal implications of this process are significant. The lender gains priority over other creditors in recovering the debt once the assignment is perfected. This means that, should the contractor default on the loan, the lender can claim the owed receivables directly from the government. Contractors can access the financing they need for project execution without needing to wait for payment, improving their cash flow and the timely completion of government projects. Finally, the government (as debtor) must be aware of the assignment because their obligation to make payments is now to the assignee (lender) once the assignment is perfected.

3.2 Pledge of a Public Contract as Intangible Asset

The pledge of a public contract as an intangible asset presents an interesting legal question, particularly in the context of OHADA law, as it involves leveraging a government procurement agreement as collateral for a loan. Although the OHADA Uniform Act on Securities allows for the pledging of intangible assets, it does not explicitly list public contracts among them. This omission raises the question whether a public contract be pledged as security under the OHADA framework.

A pledge is a contract that involves the delivery or deposit of personal property as security for a debt or obligation.³⁷ The personal property in question here is an intangible asset. The pledge of intangible assets is the assignment of an intangible asset or a set of intangible assets, existing or future, as security of one or several debts, existing or future, provided that they are specified or determinable.³⁸ In fact, pledging intangible assets as security is a common practice in modern finance, allowing businesses to leverage their contractual rights and other non-physical assets to secure financing.

The Uniform Act on Securities specifically outlines intangible moveable assets that could be pledged. These include: negotiable instruments; bank accounts; shares and shareholders rights and account of financial instruments; business property and the

³⁴ Public Contracts Code, Article 150 (3).

³⁵ *Ibid.*, the secured creditor shall notify the project owner or delegated project owner and even the accounting officer in charge of payment, of the existence of the security interest. This requirement for notification is often critical for the assignee's protection. Without this notification, the accounting officer's payment to the assignor might be considered valid, leaving the assignee to seek other more tedious means of recovering his debt.

³⁶ Uniform Act on Securities, Articles 50-51.

³⁷ Garner, B. A., (Ed) (2009), *Black's Law Dictionary*, Ninth Edition, West Thomson Reuters. P. 1272.

³⁸ Uniform Act on Securities, Article 125.

seller's preferential rights and intellectual property rights.³⁹ It is worth noting that the OHADA legislator did not mention a public contract amongst the intangible assets that could be pledged. The legislator did not however prohibit the pledging of a public contract as security for a loan. In fact, the Public Contracts Code provides that a procurement contract could be used as security, subject to any form of transfer of claim.⁴⁰

In answer to the critical question whether a public contract can be pledged, the High Court and subsequently the Court of Appeal Ouagadougou in *La Financière du Burkina (FIB) c/ Ouedraogo Fatima et le Centre Hôpitalier Universitaire Yalgado Ouedraogo (CHU-YO)*⁴¹, held the view that a public contract cannot be the object of a pledge of intangible asset.⁴² In the said case, Dame Ouedraogo Fatimata, won a contract for the delivery of goods. She proceeded to use the contract as a pledge with FIB. The secured creditor duly notified the project owner of the existence of the security as required by the law. The project owner's accounting officer overlooked the notification and proceeded to pay the contract holder for the goods delivered. The secured creditor sued both the contract holder and the project owner. At first instance the court held that a public contract cannot be the object of a pledge of intangible asset. On its part, the court of appeal held that the contract concluded between the creditor and the contract holder was rather a pledge over tangible moveable assets.⁴³ In other words, a public contract cannot be the object of a pledge of intangible asset.

Although several years ago, this case would have influenced the Cameroonian judiciary, the position above is no longer tenable today especially following the amendment of the Uniform Act on Securities to the effect that, the intangible aspect of a pledge can be founded in a debt as well as in a contract.⁴⁴ Despite the omission of a public contract as an intangible moveable asset that can be pledged, the interpretation of the Uniform Act shows that the list of pledgeable assets is not exhaustive. Despite uncertainty in the legal framework, in practice, this is the most common form of security interest created over public contracts. Concluded in the form of a synallagmatic or bilateral contract between the contract holder and a third party called the secured creditor, the latter must notify the project owner or delegated project owner and even the accounting officer of the existence of the pledge over the contract. By this, payments shall be made directly to the secured creditor to the amount given as security. Where there are several claimants, each shall receive the percentage of the claim assigned to him in the slip.⁴⁵

³⁹ *Ibid.*, Article 126.

⁴⁰ Public Contracts Code, Article 150.

⁴¹ Jugement No. 130/06 du 22 mars 2006 cited by Bahoken, V. L., *Ibid.*

⁴² Bahoken, V. L. (2017), "Le droit des suretes OHADA et les contrats publics", *PENANT, Revue Trimestrielle de Droit Africain*, Numero 901, October-December 2017, Editions Juris Africa. P. 434.

⁴³ Jugement No. 130/06 du 22 mars 2006 cited by Bahoken, V. L., *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ Bahoken, V. L. (2017), *Op. Cit.*, P. 435.

⁴⁵ Public Contracts Code, Article 150 (4), (5).

The peculiarity of pledging public contracts as security lies in the fact that it is the contract itself that constitutes the object of the pledge and a certified true copy of that contract document is handed to the creditor to perfect the security. Unlike any other pledges over intangible assets provided by the Uniform Act (e.g., bank accounts or intellectual property rights) where registration and the handing over of physical documents might be required such as certified copies of bank identification documents or certified copies of certificates of shareholdings be handed to the creditor, here, the certified copy of the contract document serves to perfect the security by providing a tangible representation of the intangible asset that is the public contract.

It is imperative to draw a distinction between a pledge of public contract and the assignment of receivables from a public contract. An assignment supposes the fact that the secured creditor can collect the accounts receivables if the contract holder does not repay the loan. On the contrary, in the case of a pledge, the pledgee is a secured creditor who gets paid directly by the accounting officer upon notification of the pledge. Considering the fact that the formality for the perfection of a security over a procurement contract is different from the procedure provided by the Uniform Act on Securities, the question that lingers is whether the non-compliance with Uniform Act prescriptions will impact the validity of the security during collective proceedings?

4. UNRAVELING THE HURDLES TO SECURITY INTERESTS IN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

The first part of this exploration laid the groundwork for a better understanding of the different forms of security interests, revealing the critical role they play in facilitating and financing public procurement and also highlighting the lack of explicit legal recognition of public contracts as security within the OHADA framework and how it poses significant legal uncertainties for creditors, contractors, and regulators alike. Consequently, the path to effectively enforcing these interests is far from straightforward. The reality is that, these obstacles impede the effective use of security interests, creating vulnerabilities and potentially jeopardizing their success in securing public projects.

Embarking on a deeper dive, this second part will project the intricacies of security interests in public procurement. Indeed, it is a complex interplay of legal frameworks, practical challenges and often conflicting legal rules. This will be an in-depth examination of these hurdles, exposing the risks they pose to prospective creditors on one hand and hopefully setting the stage for a discussion on potential solutions on the other hand.

4.1 Risks Inherent in the Use Of Public Contracts as Security: Practical and Legal Hurdles

The use of security interests in business transactions is hailed as a vector of development and a win-win arrangement between the creditor and the debtor. However, a creditor who accepts a procurement contract as a security for a loan, does so at a great risk. This risky situation is exacerbated not only by the presence of the government in the equation but also by the legal dispensation especially relating to debt recovery.

It is worth noting again that the object of the security here is a public contract concluded between a public body⁴⁶ and a private individual or firm, by which the administration hands over the execution of a public service to the private party against the payment of a fixed sum. Besides the presence of the administration and the delivery of a public service as criteria for the existence of a public contract, a public contract is notorious for the existence of “clauses exorbitantes”.⁴⁷ For example a “clause exorbitante” will give the administration the right to supervise and instruct on the performance of the contract.⁴⁸ Likewise, such a clause will give the administration the powers to inflict sanctions on its contracting partner; to unilaterally modify the terms of the contract and even to unilaterally terminate the contract.⁴⁹ The expression of these privileges and rights of the public body will greatly affect the interests of the creditor in a number of ways such as extinction of the security, delay or impossibility in payment of the receivables.

According to the Public Contracts Code, after the notification of the existence of the security to the accounting officer in charge of payment, the secured creditor benefits from the right of direct and priority payment. However, despite this right being consecrated in the law, there is the possibility that the creditor does not get paid because the accounting officer may be “unable to pay”.⁵⁰ The impossibility to effect payment may be due to lack of liquidity in the state coffers or because of constrictive economic situations, the state can decide to suspend the payment of internal debts.⁵¹ When this happens, payments due for contracts already executed are consolidated as internal debts

⁴⁶ That is the state, a decentralized entity, an administrative agency or a public institution.

⁴⁷ Gnimpieba Tonnang, E. & Mballa Emotho, B., (2013), “La qualification des contrats administratifs au Cameroun: Lecons d’une apparente evolution jurisprudentielle”, *Revue de Droit Administratif-Cameroun*, Numero 2, 1er semestre. The notion of “clauses exorbitantes” in French administrative law can be explained as any clause in a contract that is so extraordinary in character that the content is such that it will be illegal in private law of contracts. Such a clause should have the effect of conferring certain rights or creating obligations unlike those that parties in a civil or commercial transaction could freely agree upon.

⁴⁸ Craige, P. P., (1989), *Administrative Law*, London, Sweet & Maxwell, P. 497.

⁴⁹ See generally Order No. 033/CAB/PM of 13th February 2007, On General Administrative conditions applicable on public works, supplies, services and intellectual services contracts.

⁵⁰ Public Contracts Code, Article 150 (4).

⁵¹ Hooguep Tchouanguem, C., (2011), “Le Nantissement des marches publics: Etude a partir du droit OHADA”, memoire de Master en Droit des affaires et des entreprises, University of Dschang, P. 74.

of the state, to be payable at a later indeterminable date.⁵² This is a prerogative of the state and is a risk generally not foreseeable by the parties.

Another prerogative of the state is the right to unilaterally modify the terms of the contract. In fact, the contract manager has the latitude to carry out modifications judged necessary concerning all or part of the works to be executed to which the contractor must conform.⁵³ Such modifications may increase or decrease the works; suppress services, works or structures provided for in the contract; partially or totally modify the nature and quantity of all or part of the works amongst others.⁵⁴ None of these changes may cause the nullity of the contract but their possible repercussions shall be taken into account in the contractual payments. A modification of the contract will invariably affect the duration for the execution of the contract. Meanwhile the secured creditor can only be paid after the contract has been completely executed. Therefore, a prolongation of the execution of the contract due to contract modifications means he will not be paid within the time frame previously envisaged.

Furthermore, the administration's prerogatives can completely extinguish the security. The execution of any contract may be stopped before its completion, by a termination decision taken by the contracting authority.⁵⁵ The right to automatically terminate a contract may be triggered by different occurrences.⁵⁶ Sometimes, the contracting partner is entitled to compensation when the state is liable for the termination, at other times, the termination is triggered by default of the contractor. Whatever the case, a termination of the contract means the security is no longer in existence because, it is the essence of the public contract that is the object of the security agreement.

A dicer scenario is the possibility of the creditor losing his security interest to the contracting authority as a result of termination of the contract. In case of termination at the expense and risk of the defaulting contractor, another contract shall be entered into with a new contractor for the completion of the project. Any excess expenditure resulting from the execution of the new contract shall be borne by the defaulting contractor. The expenses shall be deducted from the sums which he may be due or failing that from the

⁵² Bahoken, V. L. (2017), *Op. Cit.*, P. 437.

⁵³ Order No. 033/CAB/PM of 13th February 2007, On General Administrative conditions applicable on public works, supplies, services and intellectual services contracts, Annex 1, Article 61.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, Annex 2, Article 27 and Annex 3, Article 25.

⁵⁵ General Administrative conditions applicable on public works, supplies, services and intellectual services contracts, *Op. Cit.*, Annex 1, Article 74.

⁵⁶ Public Contracts Code, Article 182 and 183. A public contract may be terminated in the following cases: death of the allottee; bankruptcy of the allottee; judicial liquidation; default of the administration's contracting partner; in case of sub-contracting, co-contracting or subsidiary orders without prior authorization; failure to comply with labour laws and regulations; price variations due to changes in economic conditions; fraudulent and corrupt practices by the contractor and in case of force majeure.

possible securities.⁵⁷ The securities in question here will refer to the performance and final bonds issued by the creditor.

Besides the risks inherent in a public contract, a secured creditor will have to navigate the complexities of recovery procedures and norms in the event where the security is extinct or payment is delayed.

4.2 The Extinction of the Specific Rights of the Creditor Subjected to Debt Recovery under OHADA Legal Framework

The secured creditor of a procurement contract who has not been paid for whatever reason, by the accounting officer has just one other option left-to requisition a refund of the loan granted to the contractor. If the contractor is able to service his debts, this will be the best scenario ever for the creditor. Unfortunately, the realities of the business world are different. The contract holder leverages the public contract as a security to obtain financing because otherwise he cannot finance the project. So, in the event where due to his fault, the contract has been terminated or due to economic constraints, the contracting authority cannot pay for the execution of the contract, the creditor can only turn to the contract holder who in this case has difficulties clearing its debts.

The OHADA law proffers a preventive settlement mechanism through which any natural or corporate person doing business and facing a difficult but not irremediable economic and financial situation, is given the possibility to clear its debts through a preventive composition agreement.⁵⁸ This collective procedure groups together all and every creditor of the debtor in question with a view to resolving their claims collectively. The secured creditor who is the holder of a public contract in the form of security, is not treated differently from other creditors. In the wake of collective proceedings, the secured creditor loses his right to direct and preferential payment.⁵⁹ Furthermore, any specific rights are jettisoned when secured creditors are regarded as part of the body of creditors, represented by the bankruptcy trustee who alone acts in the name and in the interest of the general body of creditors.⁶⁰

Despite the fact that the secured creditor has a claim guaranteed by a special security, within the framework of collective proceedings, they have no right to file an individual law suit against the debtor. Their interests are consolidated and represented by the bankruptcy trustee. Even if there was a pending law suit for the recovery of debts,

⁵⁷ General Administrative conditions applicable on public works, supplies, services and intellectual services contracts, *Op. Cit.*, Annex 1, Article 76.

⁵⁸ Uniform Act organizing collective proceedings for clearing of debts, Article 2.

⁵⁹ Public Contracts Code, Article 150 (8) provides that according to the OHADA law, creditors or claims are ranked accordingly, there are preferential claims that take precedence over the rights of secured or subrogated creditors of public contracts.

⁶⁰ Uniform Act organizing collective proceedings for clearing of debts, Article 72.

that too is automatically suspended following the launching of collective proceedings.⁶¹ This provision greatly disfavours the creditor considering the fact that there is the possibility of the debtor himself soliciting the commencement of receivership proceedings.⁶² A debtor could resort to collective proceedings to escape a pending lawsuit.

Moreover, collective proceedings culminate in the classification of security interests and the distribution of proceeds. The holder of security in public contract loses the right to direct and preferential payment. Consequently, their claim is ranked after other preferential claims such as creditors for legal costs; employees; mortgage holders and beneficiaries of general preferential rights which are subject to registration in the commerce and security register.⁶³ It is only after these other claims have been satisfied that the secured creditor shall be paid. Meaning that the creditor may face a delay or partial repayment if there are insufficient assets to cover all claims

The specific nature of a security interests on public contracts requires simply that its existence be notified to the contracting authority. On the contrary, the OHADA law on securities requires generally that security interests on personal property be registered.⁶⁴ More precisely, the decision to open proceedings puts an end to the further registration of securities held by creditors on the debtor's property. Therefore, any security interest obtained before the launching of the collective proceedings but not yet registered is estopped from doing so and consequently will not be taken into consideration during the clearing of the debtor's debts.⁶⁵ The same principle applies to securities on public contracts, that have not been notified to the accountant in charge of payment prior to the commencement of collective proceedings.

The core nature of security interests on public contracts is completely eroded in the face of collective proceedings. Regardless of the fact that this is a form of security that does not conform to the classic norms of security interests under the OHADA law, the latter's grip is so strong that at the end of the day, it is the undoing of a secured creditor and a threat to their security. There is a need to chart a path forward based on a comprehensive understanding of the specific nature of security interests in public contracts vis-à-vis the relevant OHADA laws.

5. THE WAY FORWARD- ADDRESSING THE CHALLENGES

Security in business law is absolutely crucial, acting as a bedrock for stable and predictable commercial activities. The use of public contracts as security is a daunting but trending practice in the financing of robust investment projects. It has been observed that

⁶¹ *Ibid.*, Article 75.

⁶² *Ibid.*, Article 25.

⁶³ Uniform Act on Security Interests, Articles 224 to 226.

⁶⁴ *Ibid.*, Article 50.

⁶⁵ Uniform Act organizing collective proceedings for clearing of debts, Article 73. Except of course those securities that enjoy general privileges and are exempted from the requirement of publicity.

despite the rights conferred on the holder of such security, they are unable to effectively assure the security of the creditor especially when confronted with the prerogatives of the administration on the one hand, and the extant legislation on debt recovery on the other hand. Contractors will always be in need of loans to finance procurement projects; therefore, it is imperative to have mechanisms in place that will help to mitigate the risks faced by creditors while preserving the uniqueness of this type of security.

5.1 Streamlining Administrative Prerogatives

The conclusion of a public contract gives rise to rights and obligations that binds only the parties to that contractual relationship. Likewise, a security arrangement is concluded in the form of a synallagmatic contract between the administration's contracting partner and the third party -secured creditor.⁶⁶ The former contractual relationship is governed by norms of administrative law meanwhile the latter is a civil law agreement. Despite the fact that the secured creditor is not a party to the procurement contract, their interests is invariably affected by the decisions of the administration which itself is not a party to the contract creating the security.

When the contracting authority resorts to the use of its extraordinary prerogatives either to unilaterally modify or terminate the public contract, the secured creditor's rights are severely violated. The secured creditor here is a bona fide⁶⁷ third party in every sense of the word, who has acquired rights under a contract, to the knowledge of the contracting authority. Equity demands that the contracting authority should consider how its actions are affecting or will affect third parties who have acquired rights under the contract. These prerogatives should not be used in situations where a third party has acquired rights or better still it should have no effect in a civil agreement. Such a protection can be accorded by the public contracts code and the general administrative clauses, by outlining special contractual clauses when a public contract is used as a security. A provision prohibiting the modification of the terms of the contract by the contracting authority without the express consent of the creditor could help mitigate the risk of changes to the contract's scope and duration that could delay or reduce payment to the creditor.

Moreover, the Public Contracts Code only places an obligation on the secured creditor to notify the existence of the security to the contracting or delegated contracting authority and to the accountant in charge of payment. Nothing is mentioned of a reciprocal duty on the contracting authority to give information concerning the evolution of the contract to the secured creditor. The contracting authority is the only one with verifiable and up-to-date information concerning the execution and conformity of the contract. If such information were to be put at the disposal of the creditor, they would be in a position to better anticipate the eventual modification or guard against the termination of the

⁶⁶ Public Contracts Code, Article 150 (2).

⁶⁷ The creditor is concluded the security agreement in good faith and with no intention to defraud. The default of the contractor is not his fault.

contract.⁶⁸ Likewise a contractual provision requiring advance notice of termination to the creditor would be a good step towards helping the creditor to protect his rights.

5.2 The Possibility of Substituting the Contract Holder

The challenge of securing creditors' interests in public contracts can be mitigated through legal mechanisms such as subrogation and novation, which could grant creditors more control and improve the chances of recovering owed amounts, particularly in the event of contract termination or default.

Subrogation⁶⁹ is a legal principle that enables the creditor assert the rights of the contractor against third parties, the contracting authority inclusive. The legislator through the public contracts code and the General administrative clauses applicable to all procurement contracts, should give the secured creditor the possibility of becoming a subrogated creditor. The creditor should be able to recover directly from the contracting authority, compensation due the contract holder in the event of an irregular termination of the contract.

Novation⁷⁰ is another mechanism in contract law that permits for the substitution of a party in a contract. Generally, the sale or transfer of a purely commercial contract is very common and well recognized at law. But for government contracts it is generally prohibited and any such transfer will annul the contract except where the government waives the prohibition or where the assignment occurs by operation of the law such as in the case of a merger or consolidation of firms. The general administrative clauses provide for the substitution of a defaulting contractor by the administration only. The contract holder is not given the possibility of transferring his obligations and ceding his position to a third party. It is believed that if the creditor were given the possibility of substituting a contract holder in difficulty, it will be a win-win scenario for the administration and for

⁶⁸ Coulibaly, S. (2011), "Nantissement des marches publics", available at univ-jurisocial.over-blog.com. Moroccan legislation, specifically the Dahir du 28 aout 1948 and the Circulaire No 796.SGP du 14 avril 1953 both relating to the pledge of public contracts, outlines the rights and obligations of the contracting authority and those of the secured creditor. Amongst these, the secured creditor has a right to information concerning any advance payments made by the administration to the contract holder; moreover, the contractor can request to be notified of any act susceptible to compromise the realisation of the security such as termination of the contract, bankruptcy of the contractor and judicial recovery.

⁶⁹ Garner, B. A., Op. Cit., P. 1564. Subrogation simply means substitution of one person for another; that is, one person is allowed to stand in the shoes of another and assert that person's rights against the defendant. When a party pays the debts of another, the paying party is entitled to rights, remedies or securities that would otherwise belong to the debtor.

⁷⁰ *Ibid.*, P. 1168. Novation is the act of substituting for an old obligation a new one that either replaces an existing obligation with a new obligation or replaces an original party with a new party. The only way in which it is possible to transfer contractual duties to a third party is by the process of novation, which requires the consent of the other party to the contract. In essence, novation amounts to the extinction of the old obligation and the creation of a new one.

the creditor. The object of the contract will remain the same, only the parties thereof will change.

By either of these substitution mechanisms, contract continuity and protection for both parties are guaranteed. The administration would benefit by ensuring the completion of public service contracts without a new contracting process, while the creditor would gain an opportunity to recover funds, reducing overall risks. However, the substitution mechanisms can be effective only where the contracting authority does not resort to the use of its extraordinary prerogatives either to unilaterally modify or terminate the public contract.

5.3 Preserving the Uniqueness of the Security by Exemption from the Application of OHADA Laws

The nature of security interests in public contracts is fundamentally different from classic security interests governed by OHADA law. While the OHADA laws provide a structured and standardized approach to securities, they fail to adequately address the unique characteristics of public contract securities, thus potentially undermining their effectiveness. As the rights of secured creditors of public contract are completely absorbed by the bankruptcy trustee, they become part of the mass of creditors and their claims are classified subject to the priority of preferential claims provided by the OHADA Uniform Acts.

As outlined earlier, subrogation and novation mechanisms could safeguard creditors' interests, but the full potential of these securities is only realized if the public contract securities are exempted from the rigid framework of OHADA laws which persistently robs it of its inherent values.

6. CONCLUSION

The leveraging of public contracts as security to finance robust procurement projects is both feasible, appealing and a unique prospect. The analysis in this paper reveals that despite the promise of financial security, creditors in procurement security arrangements face unpredictable challenges, including delayed or denied payments due to state liquidity issues, contract terminations that void collateral, and the subjugation of their rights under OHADA's collective proceedings framework.

To address these concerns, a re-evaluation of legal provisions governing security interests in public contracts is imperative. Protecting creditors from administrative uncertainties could be achieved through mandatory notification mechanisms, enhanced contractual protections against unilateral government actions, and the introduction of creditor substitution rights in cases of contractor default. Additionally, carving out

exceptions within OHADA's collective proceedings law for security interests in public contracts would prevent undue dilution of creditor claims.

In sum, while security interests in public procurement contracts provide an essential financial tool, their full potential remains unrealized due to existing legal and administrative hurdles. Reforming the legal framework to balance state interests with creditor protections will be crucial in fostering a more secure, efficient, and investment-friendly procurement landscape within OHADA member states. Future research should explore alternative legal models that successfully integrate public contract securities without undermining financial stability or procurement integrity.